

VACUUM AND PRESSURE BAGGINGS TO IMPROVE THE CFRP WRAPPINGS OF CONCRETE CYLINDERS

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Abstract

The vacuum bagging and pressure bagging commonly used in the aerospace industry are applied in the FRP wrapping of concrete cylinders. Both curing methods can remove the air voids within the composite wrapping during hand lay-up and develop a strong bond between the interface of concrete and FRP. Concrete specimens of designated strengths are wrapped with FRP using hand lay-up, vacuum bagging and pressure bagging, respectively, to study the applicability of these curing techniques in the retrofit of infrastructures.

In order to verify that these curing techniques can be applied to aging or deteriorated structures, concrete cylinders are axial loaded and predamaged to retain 60%, 70% and 80% of their original compressive strengths, respectively, to generate cracked and rugged surfaces. A surface treatment and primer coat are applied to smear the surface defects. FRP wrapping using both vacuum bagging and pressure bagging are conducted thereafter. The residual compressive strengths are measured to assess the performance of these two methods.

Introduction

The benefit of using FRP as a lateral confinement to improve the axial compressive capacity of concrete cylinders depends on a perfect bond between the concrete and FRP interfaces. Several attempts have been made to improve this FRP/concrete interface bonding. Winters, et.al. [1] conducted vacuum bagging and pressure bagging system after the conventional hand lay-up process to evaluate the FRP/concrete bonding performance through pull-out test of concrete columns under simulated tide in the laboratory. Test results show that pressure bagging yielded better bond than the vacuum bagging systems. Because it is difficult to obtain an air tight

seal condition, the vacuum bagging causes leaking problems in cracked concrete specimens [1]. However, the compressive strengths of the concrete columns cured by these two methods were not compared. Tai et al. [2] applied the filament and non-adhesive filament winding to wrap GFRP composites on the concrete cylinders to enhance the lateral confinement of concrete columns. Experimental results show that the non-adhesive filament winding method has higher compressive strengths as well as CAI (compression after impact) strengths than the conventional filament winding test pieces. Since the weakest link between the concrete and FRP wrapping material was excluded by the inserted aluminum foil, and the FRP can reach its highest tensile capacity [3]. In this study concrete cylinders with a dimension of 12 cm in diameter and 24 cm long were cured according to ASTM C13. The designed strength is 28 MPa. A unidirectional carbon and a hybrid carbon/Kevlar fabric were adopted for the wrapping of concrete cylinders. Hand layup, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), vatrm with non-adhesive insert methods are applied for the circumferential enhancement of the concrete specimens. After FRP wrapping and curing, the concrete cylinders were tested for their compressive capacity evaluations. Concrete cylinders were pre-compressed to 60%, 70% and 80% of their original compressive strength, and then wrapped with different techniques aforementioned to simulate the damaged concrete structures. The performance of vartm and pressure bagging are accessed through the compressive axial strength testing of pre-damaged concrete columns.

Experiment

Concrete cylinders with a design strength of 28 MPa were used as the load carrying structures. Both

CFRP (all carbon) and 4C1K (4 carbon one Kevlar yarn) fabric are applied in the lateral wrapping of concrete cylinders. The concrete cylinders were cured for 28 days in a water bath with a constant temperature of 23°C . After curing, three specimens were tested as a set for the 28-day f'_c strength of this batch. The carbon and 4C1k fabric (see Fig. 1) is provided by Formosa Taffeta company, Taiwan, with the properties listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Fabric properties

Type	weight (g/m^2)	Thickness (mm)	Strength (MPa)	E (GPa)
Carbon (TC36S)	300	0.167	4890	250
4C1K	242	0.140	4512	222

Fig. 1 Carbon and 4C1K fabrics.

For pre-damaged specimens, the cracked surface was sandblasting first, and a primer coat was applied to smear the cracks. After that a base resin was coated to improve the FRP/concrete bond before wrapping starts. For vartm, a Teflon ply, peel ply bleeder cloth, and a vacuum bag were applied after the FRP perform was held in position. In order for a uniform resin transfer, a guided sheet was inserted between the Teflon and peel ply. For non-adhesive vartm, a sheet of PVC ply was loosely attached to the outer surface of the concrete cylinder. Then a peel ply was adopted as a base ply for the vacuum bag. The rest of the process is the same as the vartm. In the vartm process a vacuum pressure of 73 cm Hg is used. During the resin transfer process, the excessive resin was collected through a by-pass tube. For pressure bagging system, a paper bag with inner

PVC bag was adopted as the bladder, and a section of a PVC tube was used as the outer constraint. The pressure was kept as 10 psi through a pressure controller (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2

After wrapping and curing, all specimens are tested for their compressive strengths. A Maekawa 200 tones compression machine is applied. The axial strain and transverse strain on the FRP hoop were recorded through Epsilon extensometers. The setup of the compression test is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Setup of a compression test

Axial compressive strength prediction for concrete columns wrapped with FRP

Lin and Li have proposed a peak stress prediction formula of concrete cylinder under FRP wrapping confinements [4]. Based upon Mohr-Coulomb's shear failure theory, the peak strength can be expressed as [4]

$$f'_{cc} = f'_c + f'_l \tan^2(45 + \phi/2) \quad (1)$$

where f'_c is the uniaxial compressive strength of concrete, f'_l is the effective confining strength and ϕ represents the internal friction angle of concrete materials. The effective confining stress should be modified according to the geometry of the concrete specimens as follows:

$$f'_l = k_c f_l \quad (2)$$

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where f_l is the confining stress, and k_c is the effective confining coefficient. For example, k_c is 0.95 for circular cross sections, and k_c equals 0.75 for rectangular cross sections [5]. The confining stress f_l can be found in [4] as:

$$f_l = \frac{2ntE_{cf}\varepsilon_{cf}}{D} \quad (3)$$

where n is the layer number of CFRP wrapping, D represents the diameter of the concrete specimen, t is the ply thickness of FRP (perform or fabric), E_{cf} is the Young's modulus and ε_{cf} is the ultimate tensile strain of FRP, respectively (see Fig. 4). Usually, the ε_{cf}

Fig. 4 FRP lateral confinement of a concrete column [4].

can be measured from the ultimate lateral FRP strain during the axial compression test of concrete specimens. From lots of axial compression experiment of concrete cylinders, the ε_{cf} is about 1% in this study, and E_{cf} depends on the constituents of FRP fabrics. The internal friction angle φ of concrete material can be expressed as

$$\varphi = 36 + 1(f_c'/35) \leq 45 \quad (4)$$

where φ is in degree and f_c' is in MPa. Equations (1)-(4) are used in the prediction of the peak compressive strengths in this study.

Results

Table 2 lists the compressive strengths of concrete columns using different wrapping techniques and fabric types. The PC stands for plain concrete without wrapping, HL is hand layup, and PB is pressure bagging. The average of this concrete batch is about 288.9 kg/cm^2 . For hybrid 4C1K wrapping, the compressive strengths range from 762 to 827 kg/cm^2 .

Table 2. Compressive strengths of concrete columns with 4C1K wrapping (fabric type H=4C1K)

fabric type-wrapping method	Prestressed % of f_c'	f_c' kg/cm^2	f_c' (kg/cm^2) (predicted)
PC	0	298.1	
PC	0	285.9	
PC	0	282.7	
C-HL-1	0	650.7	-
C-HL-2	0	676.6	-
C-HL-3	0	541.2	-
H-HL-1	0	775.9	853.2
H-HL-2	0	791.3	853.0
H-HL-3	0	793.1	853.2
H-HL-1	60	793.1	853.2
H-HL-2	60	777.6	853.0
H-HL-3	60	827.4	853.2
H-HL-1	70	762.2	853.2
H-HL-3	70	813.4	853.0
H-HL-1	80	726.1	853.2
H-HL-2	80	779.4	853.0
H-HL-3	80	801.5	853.2
H-PB-1	0	664.7	
H-PB-2	0	618.4	
H-PB-3	0	633.8	
H-PB-1	60	623.3	
H-PB-2	60	654.2	
H-PB-3	60	621.5	
H-PB-1	70	715.9	
H-PB-2	70	736.6	
H-PB-3	70	710.6	
H-PB-1	80	582.3	
H-PB-2	80	712.4	
H-PB-3	80	738.0	

Regardless to the pre-damaged percent, the HL specimens can reach almost the same peak strength (787 kg/cm^2) as the non-predamaged one (788 kg/cm^2). The error of predictive peak strengths of 4C1K HL specimens from the L-L model is less than 12% in most cases. For 4C1K HL-PB specimens, the 60% f_c' prestressed specimens have the lowest compressive strengths (633 kg/cm^2) which are close the undamaged 4C1K-HL-PB (639 kg/cm^2). This might due to experimental errors, and need further study. For 70% and 80% f_c' prestressed specimens, the peak compressive strengths increase 12.8 and 13.5%, respectively, with the undamaged 4C1K-HL-PB specimens. The difference between the undamaged 4C1K-HL-PB and 4C1K-HL is less than 2.6%.

Another set of concrete specimens with design strength of 45MPa were tested to compare the lateral confinement effect on the axial strength improvement from the vartm and non-adhesive vartm methods. Fig. 5 shows that the HL has the highest average peak strength as 93.2 MPa. While the vartm and non-adhesive vartm have an average of 75.5, and 84.3 MPa, respectively. The vartm method can reach 81% and 90% of the HL specimens. It is noted that thickness of the vartm FRP wrapping is less than the HL method. In Eq. 3, the contribution of axial compressive strength from the lateral confinement is proportional to the layer thickness as well as the lateral failure strain.

Figs. 6-7 show the compressive strengths versus axial compressive strain and lateral tensile strain in FRP wrapping, respectively. It is seen that the non-adhesive vartm has larger axial strain and lateral strain than the vartm, so the axial compressive strength has enhanced.

Conclusions

The vacuum bagging, pressure bagging and hand layup methods are used in the FRP wrapping of concrete cylinders. Through the axial compressive strength testing, the hand layup method has the highest compressive strength. The pressure bagging and non-adhesive vartm systems can reach 90% and 84% of the hand layup method.

Fig. 5 Axial compressive strengths from HL vartm and no-adhesive methods

Fig. 6 The compressive strengths and axial compressive strain from HL vartm and no-adhesive methods

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Fig. 7 The compressive strengths and lateral strain from HL varm and no-adhesive methods

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